

The Manufacture of Strychnine and Brucine from *Nux Vomica*.

BY

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When a process comes to be considered on a large scale many factors have to be considered which are usually neglected when the operations are carried out in the laboratory, such as cost of reagents, steam, and labour and initial cost of plant. For this reason the following experiments on the extraction of strychnine and brucine from *nux vomica* on a semi-large scale may be of interest.

Several processes are described in a general way in the literature. The first process tried was the extraction by dilute alcohol, evaporating off the alcohol, precipitating tannin by lead acetate and finally precipitating crude alkaloid from the filtrate by alkali. This process gave very impure alkaloid. The next process tried was one generally employed in alkaloid extraction, *viz.*, making the material alkaline and extracting with some solvent immiscible with water such as toluene or kerosene oil. The prescription used at the Government Cinchona Factory, Bengal, for the manufacture of quinine from cinchona bark was tried. This consists in mixing the material with lime and caustic soda and water and extracting with hot kerosene oil. This proved unsatisfactory as the aqueous mixture and the kerosene oil formed an obstinate emulsion.

The process was modified by mixing the powdered *nux vomica* with lime and water, drying, powdering and

extracting with hot kerosene oil. This gave a satisfactory result, but on a large scale the drying of the material is one of the most expensive parts of the process, both as regards steam and initial cost of plant. Experiments were therefore made by steaming the nuts to soften them, mixing with lime and passing through a disintegrator and extracting with hot kerosene without previous drying. This also gave a satisfactory result and the process as finally worked out was as follows.

A half-maund (41 lbs.) *nux vomica* (whole nuts) was heated in an autoclave with $1\frac{1}{4}$ times its weight of water at 30 lbs. pressure for 3 hours. Thirteen pounds of quick-lime were slaked with the surplus water from the autoclave and a little additional water until it fell to a powder. The steamed nuts were mixed with the lime and passed through the disintegrator. This material was extracted with 20 gallons kerosene at 90° in a closed pan for 1 hour with vigorous stirring and then the kerosene was separated from the mud by passing through a centrifuge. The kerosene oil was extracted with 40 lbs. dilute acid (containing 372g. sulphuric acid (D 1.81)) in a lead lined pan at 90° for 1 hour with stirring. The acid layer was run off, filtered and neutralised with a solution of 500 g. soda ash in 5 lbs. water. After standing overnight a first crop of 265 g. of alkaloid was filtered off. The mother-liquor was concentrated to one quarter of its bulk and gave a further precipitate of 93 g. of alkaloid. The alkaloid was dried in the steam-oven and extracted with its own weight of cold acetone. The residue insoluble in acetone was dissolved in hot dilute sulphuric acid and on cooling a crop of strychnine sulphate was deposited. On concentrating the mother-liquor a further crop of strychnine sulphate was obtained. On the average 6 ozs. of strychnine sulphate were obtained, but in some experiments the yield was more than this. The strychn-

nine sulphate was free from brucine. It was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. In these operations there was a loss of 2 gallons kerosene oil and of acetone equal to the weight of alkaloids treated.

The following is an estimate of the daily working expenses in handling 25 maunds *nux vomica* in a properly designed plant at Cawnpore.

	Rs.	As.
25 mds. <i>nux vomica</i> at Rs. 4-8 in Calcutta	112	8
Freight on same to Cawnpore at Rs. 2 per md.	50	0
Bags for same at as. 4 per maund ...	6	4
Carting in Calcutta and Cawnpore ...	4	0
Coal ...	17	0
Lime at Re. 1 per maund ...	8	4
Sulphuric acid (D. 1.75 at as. 2 per lb. Cawnpore) ...	6	0
Soda ash at Rs. 10-8 per cwt. (Cawnpore price)	5	4
Labour and mistri ...	12	8
25 tins kerosene oil at Rs. 3-12 ...	93	12
30 lbs. acetone at Rs. 1-8... ..	45	0
Total	360	8

The value of the product may be estimated as :—

18 $\frac{3}{4}$ lbs. strychnine sulphate at Rs. 1-10 per oz.
(London price) or Rs. 22 per lb. Rs. 409-8.

In this process it is necessary to have efficient stirring during the extraction with hot kerosene; otherwise the whole of the alkaloid is not extracted in one operation and a second extraction is necessary with increase in working charges.

Experiments have shown that the process can be further simplified by omitting the precipitation of alkaloids by soda and simply concentrating the acid-liquor, which has extracted the alkaloids from the kerosene,

when strychnine sulphate crystallises out. In this case the sulphuric acid must be cut down to 240 g. (D 1·84). From half-a-maund there was obtained 6·8 oz. strychnine sulphate free from brucine.

The recovery of pure brucine from the remaining alkaloid has not yet been worked out fully. The crude brucine extracted by cold acetone from the total alkaloids can be crystallised from 25 per cent. alcohol (decolourising with a little animal charcoal) and obtained in a pure condition.

The *nux vomica* used in these experiments contained 2·6 per cent. of total alkaloids.

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